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HYBRID EQUILIBRIUM IN N-PERSON GAMES

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Abstract. How can we combine altruism of Berge equilibrium with selfishness of Nash equilibrium? The positive answer to this question will be given below. In short, they can be combined but in the class of mixed strategies. For a noncooperative N -player normal form game, we introduce the concept of hybrid equilibrium (HE) by synthesizing the concepts of Nash and Berge equilibria and Pareto maximum. Some properties of this equilibrium are explored and its existence in mixed strategies is established under standard assumptions of mathematical game theory (convex and compact strategy sets and continuous payoff functions).

Keywords: *Berge equilibrium, Nash equilibrium, Pareto optimum, Germeier convolution, noncooperative game*

INTRODUCTION

In 1949 twenty-one years old Princeton University postgraduate J.F. Nash suggested and proved the existence of a solution [1, 2], which subsequently became known as Nash equilibrium (NE). Nash equilibrium has been widely used in economics, military science, policy and sociology. After 45 years, J. Nash together with R. Selten and J. Harsanyi were awarded the Nobel Prize in Economic Sciences “for their pioneering analysis of equilibria in the theory of non-cooperative games.” The whole point is that NE has stability against any unilateral deviations of a single player, which explains its success in economic and political applications.

Almost each issue of modern journals on operations research, systems analysis or game theory contains papers with the concept of Nash equilibrium. However, there are spots on the sun: an obvious drawback of NE consists in pronounced selfishness as each player seeks *to increase his/her/its own payoff only*.

The antipode of NE is the concept of Berge equilibrium (BE): each player applies every effort to maximize the payoffs of the other players, neglecting his/her/its individual interests. BE was formalized in 1985 by V. Zhukovskiy [3] as a possible solution of noncooperative N -player games, after perusal of C. Berge's book *Théorie générale des jeux à n personnes* [4] published in 1957 (which explains the term "Berge equilibrium"). In 1995 Russian mathematician K. Vaisman defended his Candidate of Sciences Dissertation entitled "Berge equilibrium" at Department of Applied Mathematics and Control Processes (St. Petersburg State University) under scientific supervision of Zhukovskiy. This dissertation and Vaisman's early papers [5, 6] attracted the attention of researchers, in Russia and then abroad. As of today, the number of publications related to this equilibrium has exceeded three hundreds. BE is a good mathematical model for the Golden Rule of ethics ("Behave to others as you would like them to behave to you.") [7, 8]. BE is famed for its altruism.

Obviously, these streaks – selfishness and altruism are intrinsic (in some proportion) to any individual, including a conflicting party. However, it seems delusive to expect that such a combined solution exists in pure strategies. Therefore, again following the approach of E. Borel [9], J. von Neumann [10], J. Nash [1] and their scholars, we will establish the existence of combined Nash–Berge equilibrium in mixed strategies. This solution is called hybrid equilibrium (HE). The main goal of this paper is to prove the existence of HE in mixed strategies. Also note a negative property of NE [11] and BE: the sets of both types of equilibria are internally instable, i.e., there may exist two (NE or BE) profiles such that the payoff of each player in one of them is strictly greater than in the other. We will remove this "negativity" by adding the Pareto maximality of HE with respect to all other equilibria. Well our formalization unites three properties, namely, a HE is first, *a Nash equilibrium*, second, *a Berge equilibrium*, third, *Pareto maximal with respect to the other equilibria*.

This article proves the following result: if a noncooperative N -player normal form game has bounded convex and closed strategy sets of players and also continuous payoff functions, then there exists a HE in mixed strategies in this game.

In addition, we obtain sufficient conditions for the existence of HE that are reduced to saddle point calculation for a special Germeier convolution of payoff functions.

1. FORMALIZATION OF HYBRID EQUILIBRIUM

Consider a mathematical model of a conflict as a noncooperative N -player normal form game described by an ordered triplet

$$\Gamma = \langle \mathbf{N}, \{X_i\}_{i \in \mathbf{N}}, \{f_i(x)\}_{i \in \mathbf{N}} \rangle.$$

Here $\mathbf{N} = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ denotes the set of serial numbers (indexes) of players ($N > 1$); each of N players chooses his/her/its *strategy* $x_i \in X_i \subseteq \mathbf{R}^{n_i}$, thereby forming a *strategy profile*

$$x = (x_1, \dots, x_N) \in X = \prod_{i \in \mathbf{N}} X_i \subseteq \mathbf{R}^n \quad (n = \sum_{i \in \mathbf{N}} n_i)$$

in this game; a *payoff function* $f_i(x)$ is defined over the set X , which gives *the payoff* of player i ($i \in \mathbf{N}$). At conceptual level, each player i in the game Γ seeks for choosing a strategy x_i that would *maximize* his/her/its payoff.

A natural approach is the define a solution of the game Γ using a pair

$$(x^*, f(x^*) = (f_1(x^*), \dots, f_N(x^*))) \in X \times \mathbf{R}^N,$$

where the strategies of a profile $x^* = (x_1^*, \dots, x_N^*) \in X_1 \times \dots \times X_N = X$ are determined by an optimality principle while the elements of a vector $f(x^*)$ specify the corresponding payoffs of players under these strategies. As noted by N. Vorobiev, the founder of the largest national scientific school on game theory, "...the practice of games shows that all the optimality principles developed so far directly or indirectly reflect the idea of a stable strategy profile that satisfies these principles..." [12, p. 94]. For introducing the concept of hybrid equilibrium, we will adopt three optimality principles, namely, Nash equilibrium, Berge equilibrium (from theory of noncooperative games) and Pareto maximum (PM, from theory of multicriteria choice problems). Interestingly, each of these principles has its own *type of stability*: NE is stable against the unilateral deviations of any player i (i.e., the deviations of x_i from x_i^*); BE is stable against the deviations of all players except given player i subject to the payoff function $f_i(x)$ (i.e., the deviations of $(x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}, x_{i+1}, \dots, x_N)$ from $(x_1^*, \dots, x_{i-1}^*, x_{i+1}^*, \dots, x_N^*)$); PM is stable against the deviations of all players (i.e., the deviation of the whole current profile x from the optimal solution x^*). Using the standard notation $(x \| z_i) = (x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}, z_i, x_{i+1}, \dots, x_N)$ of noncooperative games, we proceed with the following notions.

Definition 1. A strategy profile $x^e = (x_1^e, \dots, x_i^e, \dots, x_N^e) \in X$ is called a Nash equilibrium in the game Γ if

$$\max_{x_i \in X_i} f_i(x^e \| x_i) = f_i(x^e) \quad (i \in \mathbf{N}). \quad (1)$$

Definition 2. A strategy profile $x^B = (x_1^B, \dots, x_i^B, \dots, x_N^B) \in X$ is called a Berge equilibrium in the game Γ if

$$\max_{x \in X} f_i(x \| x_i^B) = f_i(x^B) \quad (i \in \mathbf{N}). \quad (2)$$

Let us associate the game Γ with the N -criteria choice problem

$$\Gamma_v = \langle X, f(x) \rangle,$$

where the set of alternatives X coincides with the set of strategy profiles X in the game Γ and the vector criterion has the form $f(x) = (f_1(x), \dots, f_N(x))$, consisting of the payoff functions $f_i(x)$ of all players $i \in \mathbf{N}$ in the game Γ .

Definition 3. An alternative (here a strategy profile $x \in X$) is Slater (Pareto) maximal in the problem Γ_v if, for all $x \in X$, the system of inequalities

$$f_i(x) > f_i(x^*) \quad (i \in \mathbf{N})$$

($f_i(x) \geq f_i(x^*)$ ($i \in \mathbf{N}$), respectively), with at least one strict inequality, is inconsistent.

Corollary 1. *It is possible to suggest the following sufficient condition of Pareto maximality: if*

$$\max_{x \in X} \sum_{i \in \mathbf{N}} f_i(x) = \sum_{i \in \mathbf{N}} f_i(x^*) \quad \forall x \in X, \quad (3)$$

then the strategy profile x^ is Pareto maximal in the problem Γ_v .*

Now, we introduce the central concept of this paper.

Definition 4. A pair $(x^*, f(x^*)) \in X \times \mathbf{R}^N$ is called a Pareto hybrid equilibrium (PHE) in the game Γ if the strategy profile x^* is simultaneously a Nash equilibrium and a Berge equilibrium in this game and also a Pareto maximal alternative in the multicriteria choice problem Γ_v , i.e., the PHE x^* satisfies three conditions as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{x_i \in X_i} f_i(x^* \| x_i) &= f_i(x^*) \quad (i \in \mathbf{N}), \\ \max_{x \in X} f_i(x \| x_i^*) &= f_i(x^*) \quad (i \in \mathbf{N}), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

x^* is Pareto maximal in Γ_v .

Remark 1. In accordance with Corollary 1, a strategy profile x^* is a PHE in the game Γ if it simultaneously satisfies the three optimality conditions (1)–(3).

Remark 2. By analogy with Definition 4, we may easily introduce the concept of Slater hybrid equilibrium (SHE), just replacing the Pareto maximality of x^* with its Slater maximality in the problem Γ_v .

2. PROPERTIES OF HYBRID EQUILIBRIA

Hereinafter, the notation $\text{cocomp } \mathbf{R}^n$ is used for the set of convex and compact subsets from space \mathbf{R}^n while $\varphi(\cdot) \in C(X)$ for a continuous scalar function $\varphi(x)$ defined over X .

In this section, let the game Γ satisfy the assumptions

$$X_i \in \text{cocomp } \mathbf{R}^{n_i}, \quad f_i(\cdot) \in C(X) \quad (i \in \mathbf{N}). \quad (5)$$

Property 1. Under conditions (5), any PHE in the game Γ is simultaneously a SHE; the set of all SHE is compact in $X \times \mathbf{R}^N$ (perhaps, empty).

Property 1 directly follows from the fact that a Pareto maximal alternative in the choice problem Γ_v is also Slater maximal (in general, the converse fails) while the set of Slater maximal alternatives X^S in Γ_v is a nonempty compact set in X [13, p. 142].

The sets of Nash and Berge equilibria, X^e and X^B , in the game Γ are also compact in X (perhaps, empty) if assumptions (5) hold. In this case, the intersection of the three compact sets $(X^S \cap X^e \cap X^B) = X^*$ is also a compact set in X (again, can be empty). The compactness of $f(X^*) = \{f(x)|x \in X^*\}$ is immediate from the continuity of the payoff functions $f_i(x)$ over X ($i \in \mathbf{N}$).

Note that the set of PHE can be noncompact, generally speaking, due to the noncompactness of the set of all Pareto maximal alternatives X^P in the choice problem Γ_v . Also keep in mind the inclusion $f(X^P) \subseteq f(X^S)$.

Property 2. Under assumptions (5), the PHE x^* satisfies the individual rationality condition, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} f_i(x^*) &\geq \max_{x_i \in X_i} \min_{x_{\mathbf{N} \setminus \{i\}} \in X_{\mathbf{N} \setminus \{i\}}} f_i(x_i, x_{\mathbf{N} \setminus \{i\}}) = \\ &= \min_{x_{\mathbf{N} \setminus \{i\}} \in X_{\mathbf{N} \setminus \{i\}}} f_i(x_i^0, x_{\mathbf{N} \setminus \{i\}}) = f_i^0 \quad (i \in \mathbf{N}), \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where $x = (x_1, \dots, x_i, \dots, x_N) = (x_i, x_{\mathbf{N} \setminus \{i\}})$, $x_{\mathbf{N} \setminus \{i\}} = (x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}, x_{i+1}, \dots, x_N)$ and $X_{\mathbf{N} \setminus \{i\}} = \prod_{j \in \mathbf{N} \setminus \{i\}} X_j$ ($\mathbf{N} \setminus \{i\} = 1, \dots, i-1, i+1, \dots, N$).

Really, each Nash equilibrium x^* in the game Γ has property 2 (individual rationality), i.e., $f_i(x^*) \geq f_i^0$ ($i \in \mathbf{N}$), where x_i^0 and f_i^0 are the maximin strategy and payoff of player i , respectively.

Remark 3. As illustrated by Vaisman's counter-example [14, pp. 68–69], individual rationality generally fails for a Berge equilibrium x^B in the game Γ .

Property 3. A PHE x^* is collectively rational in a cooperative N -player game without side payments, which appears from the Pareto maximality of the alternative x^* in the choice problem Γ_v .

Remark 4. Individual rationality applies certain requirements to alliances (coalitions) with other players: player i joins a coalition only if his/her/its payoff becomes not smaller than the maximin value f_i^0 , which can be achieved by this player independently using the maximin strategy x_i^0 .

Collective rationality drives all players to the largest payoffs (in the vector sense!) – the Pareto maximums.

As x^* is a Nash equilibrium, each player seeks to maximize his/her/its payoff.

Berge equilibrium matches an altruistic aspiration of each player for the maximal payoffs of all other players.

Actually, the first two requirements (individual and collective rationality) are among the standard criteria of “good” solutions for cooperative N -player games without side payments. At the same time, Nash and Berge equilibria are new properties for such games, which (we believe) makes the novel concept of PHE an efficient solution for the game Γ .

3. SUFFICIENT CONDITIONS

To formulate sufficient conditions for the existence of PHE in the game Γ , we will ensure Pareto maximality in terms of Definition 3 by satisfying equality (3). The sufficient conditions will be based on the original approach from [15]. Introduce an N -dimensional vector $z = (z_1, \dots, z_N) \in X$ and the Germeier convolution [16] of the form

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi_i(x, z) &= f_i(z \| x_i) - f_i(z) \quad (i \in \mathbf{N}), \\ \varphi_{i+N}(x, z) &= f_i(x \| z_i) - f_i(z) \quad (i \in \mathbf{N}), \\ \varphi_{2N+1}(x, z) &= \sum_{j \in \mathbf{N}} f_j(x) - \sum_{j \in \mathbf{N}} f_j(z), \\ \psi(x, z) &= \max_{r=1, \dots, 2N+1} \varphi_r(x, z).\end{aligned}\tag{7}$$

A saddle point $(x^0, z^*) \in X \times X$ of the scalar function $\psi(x, z)$ (7) is given by the chain of inequalities

$$\psi(x, z^*) \leq \psi(x^0, z^*) \leq \psi(x^0, z) \quad \forall x \in X, z \in X.\tag{8}$$

Theorem 1. *If (x^0, z^*) is a saddle point of the function $\varphi(x, y)$ (8) in the zero-sum two-player game*

$$\Gamma_a = \langle X, Z = X, \psi(x, z) \rangle,$$

then the maximin strategy $z^ \in X$ is a PHE of the game Γ .*

Доказательство. Really, formula (7) with $z = x^0$ gives $\psi(x^0, x^0) = 0$. Then, by transitivity,

$$\psi(x, z^*) \leq 0 \quad \forall x \in X.$$

Using $\max_{r=1, \dots, 2N+1} \varphi_r(x, z^*) \leq 0 \quad \forall x \in X$ and (7), we arrive at $2N + 1$ inequalities of the form

$$\begin{aligned}f_i(z^* \| x_i) &\leq f_i(z^*) \quad \forall x_i \in X_i \quad (i \in \mathbf{N}), \\ f_i(x \| z_i^*) &\leq f_i(z^*) \quad \forall x \in X \quad (i \in \mathbf{N}), \\ \sum_{j \in \mathbf{N}} f_j(x) &\leq \sum_{j \in \mathbf{N}} f_j(z^*) \quad \forall x \in X.\end{aligned}$$

Here the first N inequalities make $z^* \in X$ a Nash equilibrium in the game Γ (see (1)); the second group of inequalities ensures that z^* is a Berge equilibrium as dictated by (2); finally, the last $(2N + 1)$ th inequality means that z^* is a Pareto maximal alternative in the choice problem Γ_v . \square

Remark 5. In accordance with Theorem 1, PHE design is reduced to calculation of a saddle point (x^0, z^*) for the Germeier convolution $\psi(x, z)$ (7). Thus, we have developed a *constructive method* of PHE design in the game Γ , which includes the following steps:

first, define the scalar function $\psi(x, z)$ using formulas (7);

second, find a saddle point (x^0, z^*) of the function $\psi(x, z)$ (see the chain of inequalities (8));

third, calculate the values $f_i(z^*)$ ($i \in \mathbf{N}$).

Then the pair $(z^*, f(z^*) = (f_1(z^*), \dots, f_N(z^*)))$ is a PHE in the game Γ : each player $i \in \mathbf{N}$ should apply his/her/its strategy from the profile z^* , thereby obtaining the payoff $f_i(z^*)$.

Remark 6. The whole complexity of PHE design in the game Γ lies in calculation of the saddle point (x^0, z^*) for the Germeier convolution (7). The fact is that maximization of a finite number of functions $\varphi_r(x, z)$ ($r = 1, \dots, 2N + 1$) spoils the differentiability and concavity (or convexity) of $\varphi_r(x, z)$, although preserving the continuity of this function over the product $X \times Z$ of the compact sets X and Z , see [17, p. 54]. Here we face a situation well described by C. Hermite: “I turn with terror and horror from this lamentable scourge of continuous functions with no derivatives”. So it is necessary to develop numerical calculation methods for the saddle point (x^0, z^*) of the Germeier convolution $\max_{r=1, \dots, 2N+1} \varphi_r(x, z)$. Unfortunately, no literature has been found in this field of research to date. In particular, the saddle point calculation problem was not solved at the International Conference on Constructive Nonsmooth Analysis and Related Topics (CNSA-2017, St. Petersburg, May 22–27, 2017) dedicated to the Memory of Professor V. Demyanov.

4. EXISTENCE OF PARETO HYBRID EQUILIBRIUM IN MIXED STRATEGIES

One must be a reckless optimist for considering the game Γ (especially an explicit form of the payoff function) with PHE in pure strategies $x_i^* \in X_i$ ($i \in \mathbf{N}$) (by Definition 4, the desired strategy profile x^* is simultaneously a Nash equilibrium and a Berge equilibrium in the game Γ and also a Pareto maximal alternative in the corresponding choice problem). Thus, employing the approach of E. Borel [9], J. von Neumann [10], J. Nash [1] and their followers, we will extend the set X_i of pure strategies x_i to the mixed ones. Then we will establish the existence of appropriately formalized mixed strategy profiles in the game Γ that satisfy the three requirements of hybrid equilibrium.

As before, $\text{cocomp } \mathbf{R}^{n_i}$ stands for the set of all convex and compact (closed and bounded) subsets of the Euclidean n_i -dimensional space \mathbf{R}^{n_i} while $f_i(\cdot) \in C(X)$ means that a scalar function $f_i(x)$ is continuous over X .

Again consider the noncooperative N -player game Γ without side payments. Without special mention, assume the elements of the ordered triplet Γ satisfy requirements (5),

i.e.,

$$X_i \in \text{cocomp } \mathbf{R}^{n_i}, \quad f_i(\cdot) \in C(X) \quad (i \in \mathbf{N}).$$

For each compact set $X_i \subset \mathbf{R}^{n_i}$ ($i \in \mathbf{N}$), construct the Borel σ -algebra $\mathcal{B}(X_i)$, i.e., the set of all subsets of X_i such that $X_i \in \mathcal{B}(X_i)$, and $\mathcal{B}(X_i)$ is closed with respect to the complement and union of a countable number of sets from $\mathcal{B}(X_i)$; in addition, $\mathcal{B}(X_i)$ is the minimal σ -algebra that contains all closed subsets of the compact set X_i .

Therefore, construct the Borel σ -algebra $\mathcal{B}(X_i)$ for each compact set X_i ($i \in \mathbf{N}$) and the Borel σ -algebra $\mathcal{B}(X)$ for the set $X = \prod_{i \in \mathbf{N}} X_i$ of all strategy profiles, assuming that $\mathcal{B}(X)$ contains all Cartesian products of the elements from the Borel σ -algebras $\mathcal{B}(X_i)$ ($i \in \mathbf{N}$).

Within the framework of mathematical game theory, a *mixed strategy* $\nu_i(\cdot)$ of player i is identified with a *probability measure over the compact set* X_i . By definition [18, p. 271], in the notations of [19, p. 284] a probability measure is a *nonnegative* scalar function $\nu_i(\cdot)$ defined on the Borel σ -algebra $\mathcal{B}(X_i)$ of all subsets of the compact set $X_i \subset \mathbf{R}^{n_i}$ that satisfies two conditions as follows:

(1) $\nu_i \left(\bigcup_k Q_k^{(i)} \right) = \sum_k \nu_i \left(Q_k^{(i)} \right)$ for any sequence $\{Q_k^{(i)}\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$ of pairwise disjoint elements from $\mathcal{B}(X_i)$ (*countable additivity*);

(2) $\nu_i(X_i) = 1$ (*normalization*), which implies $\nu_i(Q^{(i)}) \leq 1$ for all $Q^{(i)} \in \mathcal{B}(X_i)$.

Designate as $\{\nu_i\}$ the set of all mixed strategies of player i ($i \in \mathbf{N}$).

Also note that the product measures $\nu(dx) = \nu_1(dx_1) \dots \nu_N(dx_N)$, treated in the sense of the well-known definitions of [18, p. 370] (and the notations of [19, p. 123]), are probability measures over the strategy profile set X . Let $\{\nu\}$ be the set of such probability measures (strategy profiles). Once again, we emphasize that in the design of the product measure $\nu(dx)$ the role of the σ -algebra of all subsets of the set $X_1 \times \dots \times X_N = X$ is played by the *smallest* σ -algebra $\mathcal{B}(X)$ that contains all Cartesian products $Q^{(1)} \times \dots \times Q^{(N)}$, where $Q^{(i)} \in \mathcal{B}(X_i)$ ($i \in \mathbf{N}$). The well-known properties of probability measures [20, p. 288], [18, p. 254] imply that the sets of all possible measures $\nu_i(dx_i)$ ($i \in \mathbf{N}$) and $\nu(dx)$ are *weakly closed and weakly self-compact* (see [18, pp. 212, 254], and [21, pp. 48, 49]). As applied, e.g., to $\{\nu\}$, this means that from any infinite sequence $\{\nu^{(k)}\}$ ($k = 1, 2, \dots$) it is possible to extract a subsequence $\{\nu^{(k_j)}\}$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots$) with a *weak convergence* to a measure $\nu^{(0)}(\cdot) \in \{\nu\}$. In other words, for any scalar function $\psi(x)$ that is continuous over X , we have

$$\lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \int_X \psi(x) \nu^{(k_j)}(dx) = \int_X \psi(x) \nu^{(0)}(dx)$$

and $\nu^{(0)}(\cdot) \in \{\nu\}$. Owing to the continuity of $\psi(x)$, the integrals $\int_{\mathbf{X}} \psi(x)\nu(dx)$ (the expectations) are well-defined; by Fubini's theorem,

$$\int_{\mathbf{X}} \varphi(x)\nu(dx) = \int_{\mathbf{X}_1} \dots \int_{\mathbf{X}_N} \varphi(x)\nu_N(dx_N) \dots \nu_1(dx_1),$$

and the order of integration can be interchanged.

Let us associate the game Γ in pure strategies with *its mixed extension*

$$\tilde{\Gamma} = \langle \mathbf{N}, \{\nu_i\}_{i \in \mathbf{N}}, \{f_i[\nu] = \int_{\mathbf{X}} f[x]\nu(dx)\}_{i \in \mathbf{N}} \rangle, \quad (9)$$

where, like in Γ , the set \mathbf{N} consists of all serial numbers (indexes) of players while $\{\nu_i\}$ is the set of mixed strategies $\nu_i(\cdot)$ of player i ; in game (9), each conflicting party $i \in \mathbf{N}$ chooses its mixed strategy $\nu_i(\cdot) \in \{\nu_i\}$, thereby forming a mixed strategy profile $\nu(\cdot) \in \{\nu\}$; the payoff function of each player i , i.e., the expectation

$$f_i[\nu] = \int_{\mathbf{X}} f_i[x]\nu(dx),$$

is defined over the set $\{\nu\}$.

For game (9), the notion of a PHE x^* (see Definition 4) has the following analog.

Definition 5. A mixed strategy profile $\nu^*(\cdot) \in \{\nu\}$ is called a hybrid equilibrium (HE) in the mixed extension (9) (equivalently, a hybrid equilibrium in mixed strategies in the game Γ) if

first, the profile $\nu^*(\cdot)$ is a Nash equilibrium in the game $\tilde{\Gamma}$, i.e.,

$$\max_{\nu_i(\cdot) \in \{\nu_i\}} f_i(\nu^* \parallel \nu_i) = f_i(\nu^*) \quad (i \in \mathbf{N}); \quad (10)$$

second, $\nu^*(\cdot)$ is a Berge equilibrium in game (9), i.e.,

$$\max_{\nu_{\mathbf{N} \setminus \{i\}}(\cdot) \in \{\nu_{\mathbf{N} \setminus \{i\}}\}} f_i(\nu \parallel \nu_i^*) = f_i(\nu^*) \quad (i \in \mathbf{N}); \quad (11)$$

and third, $\nu^*(\cdot)$ is a Pareto maximal alternative in the N -criteria choice problem

$$\tilde{\Gamma}_\nu = \langle \{\nu\}, \{f_i(\nu)\}_{i \in \mathbf{N}} \rangle,$$

i.e., for all $\nu(\cdot) \in \{\nu\}$, the system of inequalities

$$f_i(\nu) \geq f_i(\nu^*) \quad (i \in \mathbf{N}),$$

with at least one strict inequality, is inconsistent.

Here and in the sequel,

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_{\mathbf{N} \setminus \{i\}}(dx_{\mathbf{N} \setminus \{i\}}) &= \nu_1(dx_1) \dots \nu_{i-1}(dx_{i-1}) \nu_{i+1}(dx_{i+1}) \dots \nu_N(dx_N), \\ (\nu \parallel \nu_i^*) &= \nu_1(dx_1) \dots \nu_{i-1}(dx_{i-1}) \nu_i^*(dx_i) \nu_{i+1}(dx_{i+1}) \dots \nu_N(dx_N), \end{aligned}$$

$$\nu^*(dx) = \nu_1^*(dx_1) \dots \nu_N^*(dx_N);$$

in addition, denote by $\{\nu^*\}$ the set of hybrid equilibria $\nu^*(\cdot)$, i.e., the strategy profiles that satisfy the three requirements of Definition 5.

Consider several results used below for proving the existence of HE in mixed strategies. The following sufficient condition of Pareto maximality is obvious, see the statement below.

Proposition 1. A mixed strategy profile $\nu^*(\cdot) \in \{\nu\}$ is a Pareto maximal alternative in the choice problem $\Gamma_v = \langle \{\nu\}, \{f_i(\nu)\}_{i \in \mathbf{N}} \rangle$ if

$$\max_{\nu(\cdot) \in \{\nu\}} \sum_{i \in \mathbf{N}} f_i(\nu) = \sum_{i \in \mathbf{N}} f_i(\nu^*). \quad (12)$$

Proposition 2. Consider the game Γ under conditions (5), i.e., the sets X_i are convex and compact while the payoff functions $f_i(x)$ are continuous over $X = X_1 \times \dots \times X_N$. Let $\{\nu^e\}$ be the set of Nash equilibria $\nu^e(\cdot)$ that satisfy (10) with $\nu^*(\cdot)$ replaced by $\nu^e(\cdot)$; $\{\nu^B\}$ be the set of Berge equilibria $\nu^B(\cdot)$ that satisfy (11) with $\nu^*(\cdot)$ replaced by $\nu^B(\cdot)$; $\{\nu^P\}$ be the set of alternatives $\nu^P(\cdot)$ that satisfy (12) with $\nu^*(\cdot)$ replaced by $\nu^P(\cdot)$ (i.e., ν^P is a Pareto maximal alternative in mixed strategies in the N -criteria choice problem $\langle \{\nu\}, \{f_i(\nu)\}_{i \in \mathbf{N}} \rangle$).

Then the set $\{\nu^*\}$ of hybrid equilibria $\nu^*(\cdot)$ in the mixed extension $\tilde{\Gamma}$ of the game Γ is a weakly compact-in-itself subset of the set of mixed strategy profiles $\{\nu\}$ in the game Γ (although, $\{\nu^*\}$ can be empty).

Доказательство. Under conditions (5), we have $\{\nu^e\} \neq \emptyset$ in accordance with the Glikhsberg theorem [22]. Next, the fact $\{\nu^B\} \neq \emptyset$ has been established in the preceding sections of our book. The non-emptiness of the set of Pareto maximal alternatives, $\{\nu^P\} \neq \emptyset$, can be demonstrated by analogy. The intersection of a finite number of weakly compact sets (in our case, three ones) is also weakly compact, perhaps empty. \square

Corollary 2. Under conditions (5), the set

$$f(\{\nu^*\}) = \bigcup_{\nu(\cdot) \in \{\nu^*\}} f(\nu), f = (f_1, \dots, f_N),$$

is compact (bounded and closed) in the N -dimensional Euclidean criterion space \mathbf{R}^N .

Theorem 2 below proves the implication (5) \Rightarrow $\{\nu^*\} \neq \emptyset$, which is the central result of this article.

Proposition 3. Consider game (9) under conditions (5). Then the function $\varphi_r(x, z)$ from

$$\psi(x, z) = \max_{r=1, \dots, 2N, 2N+1} \varphi_r(x, z) \quad (13)$$

satisfies the inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_{r=1, \dots, 2N, 2N+1} \int_{X \times X} \varphi_r(x, z) \mu(dx) \nu(dz) \leq \\ & \leq \int_{X \times X} \max_{r=1, \dots, 2N, 2N+1} \varphi_r(x, z) \mu(dx) \nu(dz) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

for any $\mu(\cdot) \in \{\nu\}$ and $\nu(\cdot) \in \{\nu\}$, where

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_i(x, z) &= f_i(x|z_i) - f_i(z) \quad (i \in \mathbf{N}), \\ \varphi_j(x, z) &= f_j(z|x_j) - f_j(z) \quad (j \in \{N+1, \dots, 2N\}), \\ \varphi_{2N+1}(x, z) &= \sum_{i \in \mathbf{N}} [f_i(x) - f_i(z)]. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

This proposition was argued in [11].

Remark 7. In fact, formula (14) generalizes the well-known property of maximization: the maximum of a sum does not exceed the sum of the maximums.

Now, proceed with an interesting fact from operations research, which will be vital for proving Theorem 2. Consider $(2N+1)$ scalar functions $\varphi_r(x, z)$ ($r = 1, \dots, 2N, 2N+1$), where $z = (z_1, \dots, z_N) \in Z = X$ and $\varphi_j(x, z)$ ($j = 1, \dots, 2N+1$) are defined by (15).

Proposition 4. If $(2N+1)$ scalar functions $\varphi_j(x, z)$ ($j = 1, \dots, 2N+1$) are continuous over the product $X \times (Z = X)$ of compact sets, then the function

$$\psi(x, z) = \max_{j=1, \dots, 2N+1} \varphi_j(x, z)$$

is also continuous over $X \times Z$.

The proof of a more general result can be found in many textbooks on operations research, e.g., [17] and [23].

Finally, let us establish the central result of this article – the existence of a hybrid equilibrium (HE) in mixed strategies under conditions (5).

Theorem 2. *If in the game Γ the sets $X_i \in \text{cocomp } \mathbf{R}^{n_i}$ and $f_i(\cdot) \in C(X)$ ($i \in \mathbf{N}$), then there exists a hybrid equilibrium in mixed strategies in this game.*

Доказательство. Consider an auxiliary zero-sum two-player game

$$\Gamma^a = \langle \{1, 2\}, \{X, Z = X\}, \psi(x, z) \rangle.$$

In the game Γ^a , the set X of strategies x chosen by player 1 (which seeks to maximize $\psi(x, z)$) coincides with the set of strategy profiles of the game Γ ; the set Z of strategies z chosen by player 2 (which seeks to minimize $\psi(x, z)$) coincides with the same set X . A solution of the game Γ^a is a saddle point $(x^0, z^B) \in X \times X$; for all $x \in X$ and each $z \in X$, it satisfies the chain of inequalities

$$\psi(x, z^B) \leq \psi(x^0, z^B) \leq \psi(x^0, z).$$

Now, associate the game Γ^a with its mixed extension

$$\tilde{\Gamma}^a = \langle \{1, 2\}, \{\mu\}, \{\nu\}, \psi(\mu, \nu) \rangle,$$

where $\{\nu\}$ and $\{\mu\} = \{\nu\}$ denote the sets of mixed strategies $\nu(\cdot)$ and $\mu(\cdot)$ of players 1 and 2, respectively. The payoff function of player 1 is the expectation

$$\psi(\mu, \nu) = \int_{X \times X} \psi(x, z) \mu(dx) \nu(dz).$$

The solution of the game $\tilde{\Gamma}^a$ (the mixed extension of the game Γ^a) is also a *saddle point* (μ^0, ν^*) defined by the two sequential inequalities

$$\psi(\mu, \nu^*) \leq \psi(\mu^0, \nu^*) \leq \psi(\mu^0, \nu) \quad (16)$$

for any $\nu(\cdot) \in \{\nu\}$ and $\mu(\cdot) \in \{\mu\}$.

Sometimes, this pair (μ^0, ν^*) is called *the solution of the game Γ^a in mixed strategies*.

In 1952, I. Glikhsberg [22] established the existence theorem of a mixed strategy Nash equilibrium for a noncooperative game of $N \geq 2$ players. Applying this theorem to the zero-sum two-player game Γ^a as a special case, we obtain the following result. In the game Γ^a , let the set $X \subset \mathbf{R}^n$ be nonempty, convex and compact while the payoff function $\psi(x, z)$ of player 1 be continuous over $X \times X$ (note that the continuity of $\psi(x, z)$ is assumed in Proposition 4). Then the game Γ^a has a solution (μ^0, ν^*) defined by (16), i.e., there exists a saddle point in mixed strategies in this game.

Taking into account (13), inequalities (16) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{X \times X} \max_{j=1, \dots, 2N, 2N+1} \varphi_j(x, z) \mu(dx) \nu^*(dz) \leq \\ & \leq \int_{X \times X} \max_{j=1, \dots, 2N, 2N+1} \varphi_j(x, z) \mu^0(dx) \nu^*(dz) \leq \\ & \leq \int_{X \times X} \max_{j=1, \dots, 2N, 2N+1} \varphi_j(x, z) \mu^0(dx) \nu(dz) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

for all $\nu(\cdot) \in \{\nu\}$ and $\mu(\cdot) \in \{\mu\}$. Using the measure $\nu_i(dz_i) = \mu_i^0(dx_i)$ ($i \in \mathbf{N}$) (and hence $\nu(dz) = \mu^0(dx)$) in the expression

$$\psi(\mu^0, \nu) = \int_{X \times X} \max_{j=1, \dots, 2N, 2N+1} \varphi_j(x, z) \mu^0(dx) \nu(dz),$$

we obtain $\psi(\mu^0, \mu^0) = 0$ on the strength of (13). Similarly, $\psi(\nu^*, \nu^*) = 0$, and then it appears from (16) that

$$\psi(\mu^0, \nu^*) = 0.$$

The condition $\psi(\mu^0, \mu^0) = 0$ and the chain of inequalities (16) by transitivity give

$$\psi(\mu, \nu^*) = \int_{X \times X} \max_{j=1, \dots, 2N, 2N+1} \varphi_j(x, z) \mu(dx) \nu^*(dz) \leq 0 \quad \forall \mu(\cdot) \in \{\mu\}.$$

In accordance with Proposition 3, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
0 &\geq \int_{X \times X} \max_{j=1, \dots, 2N, 2N+1} \varphi_j(x, z) \mu(dx) \nu^*(dz) \geq \\
&\geq \max_{j=1, \dots, 2N, 2N+1} \int_{X \times X} \varphi_j(x, z) \mu(dx) \nu^*(dz).
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, for all $j = 1, \dots, 2N, 2N + 1$,

$$\int_{X \times X} \varphi_j(x, z) \mu(dx) \nu^*(dz) \leq 0 \quad \forall \mu(\cdot) \in \{\nu\}. \quad (18)$$

Consider three cases as follows.

Case I ($j = N, \dots, 2N$). Here, by (18), (15) and the normalization of $\mu(\cdot)$, we arrive at

$$\begin{aligned}
0 &\geq \int_{X \times X} \varphi_{N+i}(x, z) \mu^0(dx) \nu(dz) = \int_{X \times X} [f_i(z|x_i) - f_i(z)] \mu^0(dx) \nu(dz) = \\
&= \int_{X \times X} f_i(z|x_i) \mu^0(dx) \nu(dz) - \int_X f_i(z) \mu^0(dx) \int_X \nu(dz) = \\
&= f_i(\mu^0|\nu_i) - f_i(\mu^0) \quad \forall \nu(\cdot) \in \{\nu\} \quad (i \in \mathbf{N}).
\end{aligned}$$

By (10), $\mu^0(\cdot)$ is a Nash equilibrium in the game $\tilde{\Gamma}$ (equivalently, a Nash equilibrium in mixed strategies in the game Γ).

Case II ($j = 1, \dots, N$). Again, using (18), (15) and the normalization of $\nu(\cdot)$,

$$\begin{aligned}
0 &\geq \int_{X \times X} \varphi_i(x, z) \mu(dx) \nu^*(dz) = \int_{X \times X} [f_i(x|z_i) - f_i(z)] \mu(dx) \nu^*(dz) = \\
&= \int_{X \times X_i} f_i(x|z_i) \mu(dx) \nu_i^*(dz) - \int_X f_i(z) \mu(dz) \int_X \nu^*(dz) = \\
&= f_i(\mu|\nu_i^*) - f_i(\nu^*) \quad \forall \mu(\cdot) \in \{\nu\} \quad (i \in \mathbf{N}).
\end{aligned}$$

On the strength of (11), the mixed strategy profile $\nu^*(\cdot)$ is a Berge equilibrium in the game Γ by Definition 5.

Case III ($j = 2N + 1$). Again, using (18), (15) and the normalization of $\nu(\cdot)$ and $\mu(\cdot)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
0 &\geq \int_{X \times X} [\sum_{r \in \mathbf{N}} f_r(x) - \sum_{r \in \mathbf{N}} f_r(z)] \mu(dx) \nu^*(dz) = \\
&= \int_X \sum_{r \in \mathbf{N}} f_r(x) \mu(dx) \int_X \nu^*(dz) - \int_X \mu(dx) \int_X \sum_{r \in \mathbf{N}} f_r(z) \nu^*(dz) = \\
&= \sum_{r \in \mathbf{N}} f_r(\mu) - \sum_{r \in \mathbf{N}} f_r(\nu^*) \quad \forall \mu(\cdot) \in \{\nu\}.
\end{aligned}$$

In accordance with Proposition 1 and (12), the mixed strategy profile $\nu^*(\cdot) \in \{\nu\}$ of the game Γ is a Pareto maximal alternative in the multicriteria choice problem

$$\tilde{\Gamma}_v = \langle \{\nu\}, \{f_i(\nu)\}_{i \in \mathbf{N}} \rangle.$$

Thus, we have proved that the mixed strategy profile $\nu^*(\cdot)$ in the game Γ is simultaneously a Nash equilibrium and a Berge equilibrium that satisfies Pareto

maximality. Hence, by Definition 5, the mixed strategy profile $\nu^*(\cdot)$ is a hybrid equilibrium in the game Γ . \square

Remark 8. Note that a bimatrix games do not satisfy the conditions of Theorem 2.

CONCLUSION

In this work, we propose a new concept of equilibrium. It combines the concepts of Nash and Berge equilibria and Pareto maximum. In the future, we hope to develop constructive methods for constructing this equilibrium.

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